

Notes on the white running spider *Gephyrota glauca* (Jézéquel, 1966) from South Africa (Araneae: Philodromidae)

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ABSTRACT: *Gephyrota glauca* (Jézéquel, 1966) is an African endemic species known from the Ivory Coast, Cameroon, and South Africa. It is a plant-dwelling species frequently found on vegetation. This article provides information on its general morphology, behaviour, and distribution in South Africa, along with photographs of live specimens.

Keywords: biodiversity, conservation biography, South African National Survey of Arachnida.

INTRODUCTION

Many Philodromidae were sampled during the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa) (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015). Six genera, represented by 34 species, are known from South Africa (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2022). Although large numbers of specimens were collected, many can still not be identified, and the number of genera and species might increase after revisions. Presently, only *Tibellus* Simon, 1875, has been revised (Van den Berg & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1994).

The philodromid genus *Gephyrota* Strand, 1932 with the type species *Gephyra limbata* L. Koch, 1875 was described from Australia. However, the generic name *Gephyra* was preoccupied, and a replacement name, *Gephyrota*, was provided (Strand, 1932). Currently, seven species are recognized from Africa, Australia, India, and Vietnam (World Spider Catalog, 2024). Very little is still known about the genus, as six of the seven species are known only from their original descriptions made between 1875 and 1909, and three species' descriptions are based only on juvenile specimens.

Only *Gephyrota glauca*, described by Jézéquel (1966) from Ivory Coast, is known from both sexes. The species has been recorded from Cameroon and South Africa (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2022). This paper provides more information on their general behaviour, distribution, and morphology, and some colour variations are discussed based on photographs of live specimens.

METHODS

Voucher specimens ($n=45$) sampled during SANSa surveys are housed in the National Collection of Arachnida (NCA) at the Agricultural Research Council (ARC) in Pretoria. As part of SANSa requests for photographs of spiders for the SANSa Virtual Museum were made (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2012). Several sets of photographs of the species were received from the public.

TAXONOMIC NOTES

Gephyrota glauca (Jézéquel, 1966)

Gephyra glauca Jézéquel, 1966: 621 (mf).

Gephyrota glauca Brignoli, 1983: 599; Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2022: 6.

Diagnostic characteristics: Size: TL females and males 4-6 mm. Female (Figs 1 & 2): Carapace with white border and two grey lateral bands; integument covered with a layer of dense white setae; clypeus with strong white setae on the border (Fig. 3). The carapace is round, wider than long, slightly narrower in eye region; cephalic region slightly raised; eyes equal-sized, both eye rows recurved; posterior eye row wider than anterior row with eyes equally spaced; anterior row with median eyes closer to anterior lateral eyes than to each other (Fig. 2). Abdomen white with integument covered with dense layer of setae (Fig. 4);

Figures 1–2. *Gephyrota glauca* female. 1. Female from Pretoria (Clarissa van Heerden). 2. Female from Hermannsburg (Peter Webb).

abdomen uniform white sometimes with scattered dark spots around apodemes; the edge of the abdomen sometimes with brownish red markings that vary from a few spots (Figs 4–7) to distinct markings (Fig. 8). The abdomen is oval, pointed towards spinnerets. Legs almost translucent and covered with dense white setae, leg II slightly longer than others. Epigyne: (Figs 9–10). Male: resembles female (Fig. 5). Palp. (Fig. 11).

BEHAVIOUR

Gephyrota glauca is a plant-living spider that has a range of characteristic adaptations that facilitate life on bark, in grass, in flowers, among foliage or on seeds, and sometimes on the ground (Fig. 4). They were commonly found in sweep net and beating samples but also from pitfall traps. Haddad (2016) sampled them from *Vachellia xanthophloea* bark in the Ndumo Game Reserve. They feed on a variety of insects (Fig. 8). Their movements are erratic but swift, and their claw tufts and scopulae enable speedy movement on vegetation. Their laterigrade legs and flat bodies allow them to hide in crevices.

HABITAT

The species has been collected in the Forest, Fynbos (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2024), Savanna (Foord *et al.*, 2011), Indian Ocean Coastal Belt and Thicket biomes. It was also sampled from macadamia and pistachio orchards, sunflower and tomatoes (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2013).

DISTRIBUTION

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Cameroon, Ivory Coast, South Africa.
New records: Pom Pom Camp, Okavango Delta (-19.578, 22.841 NCA); Zimbabwe (iNaturalist).

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Addo Elephant National Park (-33.32, 25.72); East London (-33.01, 27.9); Ongeluksnek (-30.55, 28.57); East London (Pineapple Research Station) (-33.01, 27.9); Hogsback (-32.59, 26.92); Thyspunt, 12km WNW of Cape St Francis (-34.18, 24.74). **Free State:** Erfenis Dam Nature Reserve (-28.5, 26.8); Kalkfontein Dam Nature Reserve (-29.518, 25.268); Wyndford Guest Farm, Fouriesburg (-28.7, 28.24); Amanzi Nature Reserve (-28.62, 26.68); Mpetsane Conservation Estate (near Clocolan) (-28.80, 27.65). **Gauteng:** Pretoria/Tshwane (-25.74, 28.19); Klipriviersberg Nature Reserve (-26.27, 28.08); Pretoria National Botanical Garden (-25.74, 28.19); Irene (field opposite Gem Village) (-25.89, 28.23); Ezemvelo Nature Reserve (-25.700, 28.941). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Cathedral Peak (-28.94, 29.19); iSimangaliso Wetland Park: Hell's Gate (-28, 32.48); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Kloof (-29.78, 30.83); Good Hope Plantation, Boston Midlands (-29.651, 29.976); Wakefield Farm (-29.4733, 29.8925); Vernon Crookes Nature Reserve (-30.27, 30.57). **Limpopo:** Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve (-23.82, 30.16); Little Leigh (Western Soutpansberg) (-22.9485, 29.86961); Medike Mountain Reserve (-22.994, 29.614). **Mpumalanga:** Blyde River Canyon Nature Reserve (-24.58, 30.82). **Northern Cape:** Nieuwoudtville (-31.37, 19.11); Prieska (-29.68, 22.74); Rooipoort Nature Reserve (-28.56, 24.16); Tswalu Game Reserve (-27.30, 22.44). **Western Cape:** Bloubergstrand (-33.77, 18.45);

Figures 3–11. *Gephyrota glauca* 3. Eye pattern dorsal view (P. Webb). 4. Female from Kalkfontein Dam Nature Reserve (N. Josling). 5. Male from Pretoria (Clarissa van Heerden). 6. Female from Hermannsburg (Peter Webb). 7. Female from Mpetsane Conservation Estate (Allen Jones). 8. Female (Wolf Avni). 9. A.S. Dippenaar-Schoeman. 10–11. After Jézéquel (1966).

Cape Agulhas (-34.81, 19.81); Cederberg Wilderness Area (-32.16, 18.89); Fisherhaven, Hermanus District (-34.47, 19.27); Paarl (-33.71, 18.98); Swartberg Nature Reserve (-33.36, 21.69); Yzerfontein (-33.34, 18.16); Robben Island (-33.80, 18.35); Fernkloof Nature Reserve, Hermanus (-34.61, 19.34); Kogelberg Biosphere Reserve (-34.32, 18.96); Bloubergstrand (-33.77, 18.45); Uitzicht Annex Knysna (-34.00, 23.20); Robben Island (-33.80, 18.35).

CONSERVATION

An African endemic described in 1966 from Ivory Coast and recorded from several African countries. In South Africa it has been recorded from eight provinces, including the following areas: Addo Elephant National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2020); Hogsback (Haddad *et al.*, 2023); Thyspunt (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Wiese (2020); Erfenisdam Nature Reserve (Fourie *et al.*, 2013); Ndumo Game Reserve (Haddad, 2016); Tswalu Kalahari Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2018); Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve (Foord *et al.*, 2016). Due to its wide range it is listed as Least Concern.

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